

Supra-subduction zone ophiolites retain hydrogen generation potential after 300 million years

Frédéric V. Donzé*¹ and Laurent Truche¹

*Corresponding author e-mail: frederic.donze@univ-grenoble-alpes.fr

Affiliations

¹Univ. Grenoble Alpes, Univ. Savoie Mont Blanc, CNRS, IRD, Univ. Gustave Eiffel, ISTerre,
38000 Grenoble, France

Abstract

The Ural Mountains host some of the earliest documented natural hydrogen (H₂) emissions, yet the Paleozoic ultramafic complexes are 250–400 Ma old and would normally be expected to have exhausted their serpentinization potential. We revisit overlooked Soviet observations from the Kempirsay chromitite district and compare them with recent data from the younger, Jurassic Bulqizë ophiolite in Albania. In both massifs, H₂-rich seeps (>80–90 vol% H₂) occur within ~300 m of podiform chromitite bodies. At Kempirsay, degassing takes place at low temperatures (14–30 °C), and experiments on Kempirsay rocks show that Fe-bearing minerals can generate H₂ at near-ambient conditions. New radiocarbon data from Bulqizë methane (3.76 ± 0.06 pMC, apparent age ~26 kyr) demonstrate that associated CH₄-H₂ inventories are renewed on 10⁴-year timescales. We interpret chromitite bodies and their damage zones as catalytic and hydraulic hubs embedded in a supra-subduction-zone ophiolitic architecture that localizes serpentinization and preserves reactive peridotite. This chromitite-centered architecture implies that chromitite-bearing mantle slabs can retain hydrogen generation potential for hundreds of millions of years and constitute priority targets for natural hydrogen exploration and stimulated geological hydrogen production.

Keywords

Natural hydrogen seeps; Chromitite-bearing ophiolites; Low-temperature serpentinization; Chromitite-hosted H₂-CH₄ fluids; Geological hydrogen systems

Main Text

Introduction

Recent mining accidents in Kazakhstan's chromite mines have brought renewed attention to the persistent hydrogen hazard in these ancient geological formations. In February and May 2025, fires at the "Bolashak" mine injured several workers, forcing operational suspensions and highlighting a phenomenon that has plagued these mines for decades (Interfax, 2025a, b; Kursiv, 2025, ISSSource, 2025; Yermaganbetova, 2025). These incidents echo observations dating back to 1979 from the same mining district, when hydrogen-rich gas ignited underground, creating what miners described as "calm flames over 12 m high" (Ukhanov et al., 1987). The first documented observations of H₂-rich gas (66.5-81 % H₂) in Ural mines date from 1925-1931 and were reported by Zavaritsky, Tchepennikovs and Vernadsky (Lidin et al., 1982; Bohdanowicz, 1934), in the Nizhny Tagil dunite massif during drilling operations for chromite exploration at ~600 m depth. Soviet research, often overlooked in Western literature, provided the following additional observations. Lidin et al. (1982) noted that hydrogen emissions at the Kempirsay massif occurred exclusively within 300 meters of chromitite bodies and were never reported in barren ultramafic units. The isotopic signatures were also unusual: Ukhanov et al. (1987) measured some of Earth's most negative δD values (-744 to -766 ‰), which they interpreted as evidence for low-temperature processes. Devirtz et al. (1992) experimentally demonstrated hydrogen production from Kempirsay ultramafic rocks at ambient temperatures of 17-24 °C, suggesting that serpentinization reactions may be faster than commonly thought in chromite-rich geological environments.

The persistence of hydrogen degassing from Paleozoic ophiolites in the Ural Mountains highlights gaps in our understanding of natural hydrogen systems. These ultramafic complexes, 250–400 Ma old, should have exhausted their serpentinization potential long ago, through migration, microbial or abiotic consumption, yet they still release hydrogen at rates that rival much younger systems. These observations closely parallel those from

the Bulqizë mine, hosted in a Jurassic ophiolite approximately 170 Ma old, where active hydrogen seeps persist within chromitite-bearing peridotites (Truche et al., 2024, 2025; Yao et al., 2025). The fact that ophiolites spanning such a wide age range, from Paleozoic to Mesozoic, show similar degassing patterns raises the question of how chromitites control natural H₂ systems in chromitite-bearing SSZ ophiolites worldwide. Without ruling out the possibility that part of the present-day hydrogen emissions reflect older serpentinization events that are now extinct, we address this question by examining several features of these ophiolites that may support long-lived and still active H₂ systems. A first-order observation is that both Kempirsay and Bulqizë share a common geological heritage: they are supra-subduction ophiolites that host abundant podiform chromitites. Podiform chromitites form in such settings during high-degree partial melting of the mantle wedge, and concentrate chromium-rich minerals and associated phases that can strongly influence redox conditions. Similar associations between chromitite bodies and hyperalkaline H₂-CH₄ fluids have been documented in several other chromitite-bearing ophiolites worldwide, suggesting that chromitite-bearing ophiolites of this type may represent a coherent class of natural hydrogen systems. In this study, we use a comparative analysis of the Kempirsay and Bulqizë ophiolites to document this class of chromitite-bearing systems and assess their implications for natural hydrogen generation and exploration.

Geological Setting and Hydrogen Occurrences in Ural and Bulqizë chromite mines

The Ural Mountains exhibit numerous ophiolitic complexes that originate from the oceanic lithosphere formed during the Paleozoic evolution of the Uralian Ocean between 400-250 Ma (Brown et al., 2006; Puchkov, 2009). These complexes were obducted during the Late Devonian-Early Carboniferous collision between the Baltica and Siberia-Kazakhstan continents (Spadea & D'Antonio, 2006). Among these, the Kempirsay massif in Kazakhstan stands out as one of Earth's largest exposed ultramafic complexes, covering over 900 km². Within the Sakmara allochthon, it represents fore-arc lithosphere formed along the Devonian Magnitogorsk Island arc (Savelieva et al., 1997; Fryer & Greenough, 1992, Johnson, 2012). To understand the significance of hydrogen emissions from such ancient rocks, we can compare them with the much younger Bulqizë ophiolite in Albania (Table 1). This Jurassic complex

formed 160-165 million years ago in a Neo-Tethyan setting (Beccaluva et al., 1994; Dilek & Furnes, 2009), provides an interesting contrast.

Table 1. Comparative characteristics of H₂-producing ophiolitic systems (references for the values are provided in the text)

Parameter	Kempirsay (Urals)	Bulqizë (Albania)	Implications
Geological features			
Ophiolite age	250-400 Ma	160-165 Ma	200+ Ma age difference
Geothermal gradient	~12°C/km	25-30°C/km	Distinct thermal regimes
Temperature assessment at H ₂ source depth	14-30°C	100-150°C	Different generation conditions?
Degree of serpentinization	~28% (historical estimate)	<2% in harzburgite	Substantial fresh rock remains
Gas characteristics			
δD-H ₂ (‰ VSMOW)	-744 to -766	-743 ± 3	Remarkably similar signatures
H ₂ concentration	92-98%	84 ± 4%	Both highly enriched
CH ₄ content	0.8-1.7%	13.2 ± 0.7%	Variable secondary processes
Maximum documented H ₂ flux 20 m ³ /day		~550 m ³ /day	Different scales or preservation?

Parameter	Kempirsay (Urals)	Bulqizë (Albania)	Implications
Association with chromitite location	100%	100%	Comparable spatial control

Kempirsay and Bulqizë share similarities like both hosting large podiform chromitites surrounded by dunite envelopes. They both display persistent H₂ seepages, with gas compositions > 80 % H₂ (92–98 % in Kempirsay, 84 % in Bulqizë). However, they differ on some other points. Firstly, the Kempirsay ophiolitic massif exhibits exceptionally low surface heat flow values of 25-35 mW m⁻² (mean ~30 mW m⁻²), significantly below the global continental average of ~65 mW m⁻² (Kukkonen et al., 1997; Brown et al., 2006; Golovanova, 2005; Krabbendam, 2001). Direct temperature-depth profiles from boreholes and the URSEIS (Urals Reflection Seismic Experiment and Integrated Studies project) geothermal model indicate a present-day crustal thermal gradient of ~12°C km⁻¹ (10-15°C km⁻¹ in the upper 2 km) (Mikhailov et al., 2002). This anomalously cold geothermal regime reflects the combined effects of low crustal heat production (~0.45 μW m⁻³), thick lithosphere inherited from Paleozoic collision, and residual Quaternary glacial cooling. By contrast, the Bulqizë ophiolitic massif displays higher surface heat flow values of 45-50 mW m⁻², above the Albanian national average of 30-40 mW m⁻² (Frashëri, 2015). Direct measurements inside the Bulqizë mine indicate steep thermal gradients of 25-30°C km⁻¹ in the upper 2-3 km (Goskolli, 2022), corresponding to temperatures higher than ~100 °C at depths of a few kilometers (Yao et al., 2025). Secondly, the degree of serpentinization could be quite different in the two mines. Historical mapping suggested that ~28 % of the Kempirsay peridotite was serpentinized (Lidin et al., 1982). Subsequent core drilling and bulk-rock LOI (“Loss On Ignition”) measurements, indicate that the upper-most kilometer is now almost completely serpentinized (70–100 %, LOI = 10–17 wt %), with fresh lherzolite restricted to depths > 1 km (Saveliev et al., 2022). At Bulqizë, petrographic mapping shows that most harzburgite and dunite are still largely unaltered (< 2 % serpentine) on the first km, with hydration restricted to chromitite-bearing fault corridors (Xiong et al., 2015). Inside these corridors, the alteration intensity rises from dunite envelopes to massive chromitite, reflecting possible multiple serpentinization pulses and late fluid percolation (Junge et al., 2021).

The spatial distribution of hydrogen emissions provides insights into the controlling factors of these ancient systems. At the Kempirsay massif, detailed underground mapping by Soviet geologists documented a well-defined pattern: all hydrogen occurrences clustered in the immediate vicinity of chromitite ore bodies. The Molodezhnaya mine exemplified this relationship, producing sustained flows reaching $20 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$ from discrete fracture systems adjacent to chromitite lenses. Gas composition showed extreme hydrogen enrichment (92-98%) with minor methane (0.8-1.7%) and nitrogen (0.4-0.6%), plus trace helium, similar to the 84% H_2 observed at Bulqizë (Truche et al., 2025) despite the vast differences in age and temperature of the ophiolite environment.

Strong support for low-temperature generation comes from Soviet experimental work that has received insufficient attention in recent literature. Devirtz et al. (1992) subjected Kempirsay rock samples to controlled laboratory conditions, demonstrating hydrogen production at both $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and at ambient temperatures between 17 and $24 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Similar low-temperature hydrogen generation has been reported from other serpentinizing systems (Mayhew et al., 2013; Neubeck et al., 2014; Ellison et al., 2021), though the specific role of chromitites as catalytic enhancers remains underexplored. The detection of radiocarbon in methane from Bulqizë represents an additional constraint on the timescales of these systems (Truche et al., 2025). The measured value of $3.76 \pm 0.06 \text{ pMC}$, corresponding to an apparent age of $\sim 26 \text{ 000}$ years, shows that at least part of the CH_4 inventory is renewed on 10^4 -year timescales rather than the 10^6 -year scales often assumed for ophiolitic systems. The young age of CH_4 implies that the associated H_2 required for its synthesis must also be recently produced, indicating active, ongoing hydrogen generation rather than simple release of ancient gas reservoirs. This suggests that chromitite-bearing SSZ ophiolites may play a more dynamic role in the global carbon and hydrogen cycles than previously recognized.

These observations are consistent with the idea that low-temperature serpentinization can sustain hydrogen generation under appropriate geochemical conditions, but they do not by themselves explain why active seeps in both massifs are strictly confined to the vicinity of chromitite ore bodies; this is the question we now address in the following discussion.

The Chromitite Catalytic Factory

The association between hydrogen emissions and chromitite bodies at Kempirsay and Bulqizë reflects more than spatial coincidence. In both massifs, all documented H_2 -rich seeps are located within a few hundred meters of podiform chromitite, whereas no comparable

degassing has been reported within the same type of ophiolites without chromitite despite similar ultramafic host rocks (Donzé et al., 2024). This spatial pattern suggests that chromitites and their surrounding damage zones play a central role in both H₂ production and migration. First, chromitite bodies can act as mechanically stiff inclusions that focus fracturing and maintain damage zones within a more deformable peridotite–serpentinite matrix, thereby providing permeable pathways for infiltrating meteoric water and for the escape of produced gas. In addition to this mechanical role, chromitite-bearing peridotites also provide favorable redox and catalytic conditions for hydrogen generation. At the mineral–fluid interface, Fe(II)-rich spinel surfaces (chromite, magnetite) can catalyze hydrogen generation by transferring electrons from structural and adsorbed Fe(II) to water molecules and protons adsorbed on the spinel surface, thereby reducing water to H₂ while oxidizing Fe(II) to Fe(III) (Mayhew et al., 2013). Sustained H₂ production can occur as dissolution of neighboring Fe(II)-bearing silicates replenishes aqueous Fe²⁺ that sorbs onto spinel surfaces and is repeatedly oxidized, until secondary Fe(III)-(hydr)oxide or silica-rich coatings passivate the spinel and inhibit further electron transfer.

Similar associations have been reported in other chromitite-bearing ophiolites worldwide (Figure 1). Beyond Kempirsay and Bulqizë, similar associations between chromitite bodies and hyperalkaline H₂–CH₄ fluids have been documented in at least a dozen ophiolitic massifs, spanning the Dinarides–Hellenides belt (Krivaja–Konjuh, Ozren, Borja, Othrys, Argolida), the eastern Mediterranean (Troodos, Tekirova, Kızıldağ, Tişovița), and further afield (Zambales, Cedars, Elba) (Etiopie et al., 2013, 2017, 2018; D'Alessandro et al., 2018; Neal & Shand, 2002; Sciarra et al., 2022; Morrill et al., 2013; Aquino et al., 2025). Although the chromitite–H₂ system connection has not been directly documented in the Oman ophiolite, this case provides additional insights through numerous hyperalkaline springs where H₂-rich gas bubbles and podiform chromite deposits serve as indicators, with some chromitite bodies being closely associated with H₂ emission points (Neal and Stanger, 1983; Augé, 1987; Rollinson, 2005; Leong et al., 2021; Pasquet et al., 2024; Templeton et al., 2024). Occluded H₂ and CH₄ have also been measured directly within chromitite samples from Bulqizë and Othrys ophiolites (Truche et al., 2024; Etiopie, 2024; Pappalardo et al., 2025). In many of these systems, CH₄ is interpreted as a secondary product of Fischer–Tropsch-type reactions fueled by H₂, further emphasizing the central role of chromitite-hosted catalytic interfaces. All these observations indicate that the association between chromitite occurrence and reduced H₂-bearing fluids is not restricted to our two case studies, but appears recurrent in chromitite-

bearing SSZ ophiolites. However, Kempirsay and Bulqiz remain, to our knowledge, the only systems where the spatial relationship between active H₂ seeps and mapped podiform chromitite bodies has been quantified at local (10²–10³ m) scale; systematic surveys in other ophiolites will be required to test how general this tight coupling is.

Figure 1. Global distribution of Neoproterozoic and Phanerozoic ophiolite belts, modified after Vaughan & Scarrow (2003). Supra-subduction-zone ophiolites that host podiform chromitites and reduced H₂–CH₄-rich fluids discussed in this study are highlighted, including the Kempirsay massif in the Urals (Kazakhstan), the Bulqiz ophiolite (Albania) and other chromitite-bearing peridotite massifs cited in the text.

Beyond this first-order picture, several features of podiform chromitites may further enhance hydrogen generation. During fluid-related alteration, chromite (FeCr₂O₄) commonly develops Fe-rich ferritchromite and Cr-rich magnetite rims, reflecting progressive Fe enrichment and oxidation of the spinel (Ahmed & Surour, 2016). More generally, in serpentinizing ultramafic rocks, oxidation of ferrous iron in Fe(II)-bearing minerals is widely recognized to generate H₂-rich fluids (e.g. Holm et al., 2015; Barbier et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2016; Preiner et al., 2018). Chromitites are also enriched in platinum-group elements by one to two orders of magnitude relative to surrounding peridotites (Melcher et al., 1997), creating metal-rich interfaces where catalytic water reduction and Fischer–Tropsch-type reactions may be promoted (Dutoit et al., 2025; Truche et al., 2025; Oze et al., 2007). Quantifying the contribution of these mineralogical and catalytic effects, however, will require dedicated experimental and field studies beyond the scope of this work.

Chromitite bodies thus operate as local catalytic and hydraulic hubs. Their role can be understood within the broader architecture of supra-subduction-zone ophiolites, focusing on how their inherited architecture controls both the early localization of serpentinization and the long-term preservation of reactive mantle domains.

Mineralogical and structural drivers of chromite-hydrogen coupling in SSZ ophiolites

Supra-subduction-zone (SSZ) ophiolites create a distinctive mantle architecture in which podiform chromitites, strongly depleted peridotites and inherited permeability structures are closely intertwined (Pearce et al., 1984; Dilek & Furnes, 2011). High-degree melting and melt–rock interaction in fore-arc settings produce harzburgite–dunite domains that are both olivine-dominated and Fe²⁺-bearing, providing a chemically favorable substrate for H₂-producing reactions once hydration occurs (Pearce et al., 1984; Dilek & Furnes, 2011). At the same time, SSZ magmatism focuses Cr-rich melts into deforming peridotite to form podiform chromitites, while faulting and dyke emplacement imprint a heterogeneous network of fractures, magmatic contacts and damage zones that control where seawater can initially penetrate the lithospheric mantle (Dilek & Furnes, 2011; Parkinson, 1998; Maulana et al., 2015). In this configuration, serpentinization is expected to be strongly localized along a subset of these inherited high-permeability structures, rather than proceeding uniformly throughout the mantle section (Mével, 2003; Rouméjon et al., 2015; Aupart et al., 2021). Early hydration along faults, shear zones, gabbro–peridotite contacts and dyke swarms, creates serpentinite corridors that become mechanically weak and highly permeable, concentrating both deformation and fluid flow during subsequent intra-oceanic subduction and obduction (Rouméjon et al., 2015; Cox et al., 2021; Tarling et al., 2019). By contrast, intervening blocks of harzburgite–dunite and gabbro that remain less fractured and only weakly hydrated behave as more competent panels and can be translated upward largely as coherent blocks, with limited additional serpentinization during exhumation (Evans et al., 2021; Tarling et al., 2019). This behavior, for example well-illustrated by field relationships in East Sulawesi, shows that the preservation of relatively “dry” ophiolitic fragments to the surface is not the absence of serpentinization, but rather the consequence of its early localization along discrete shear zones (Parkinson, 1998; Maulana et al., 2015).

Once obducted and exposed at shallow crustal levels, these preserved olivine-rich blocks are reconnected to meteoric water through fault networks inherited from the same tectonic

history (Evans et al., 2021; Dilek & Furnes, 2011). At this late stage, large volumes of Fe^{2+} -bearing peridotite that escaped pervasive hydration during subduction become available for renewed low-temperature serpentinization and chromitite-catalyzed water reduction. Combined with the thick, permeable architecture typical of obducted SSZ mantle slabs, this interplay of early localization of serpentinization, mechanical partitioning of strain, and long-term preservation of reactive mantle domains makes these ophiolites particularly effective natural systems for sustaining hydrogen generation potential over hundreds of millions of years (Pearce et al., 1984; Dilek & Furnes, 2011; Evans et al., 2021).

Implications for Natural Hydrogen Systems

Chromitite-bearing SSZ ophiolites behave as poly-stage hydrogen systems initiated at oceanic spreading centers through mantle exhumation and seawater penetration along detachment, transform, and normal fault networks. During active subduction, hydration of the mantle wedge along inherited faults and shear zones in the forearc localizes serpentinization and the production of reduced fluids. The Mariana forearc provides a modern analogue of this stage: serpentinite mud volcanoes there are fed by fluids released from the subducting Pacific Plate and discharge high-pH (up to 12.5) fluids enriched in abiotic H_2 , CH_4 and higher hydrocarbons (Miladinova et al., 2023; Wheat et al., 2020). These reduced gases are attributed to serpentinization-driven hydrogen production, coupled with abiotic methane synthesis. Similar forearc processes likely operated during the SSZ stage of ophiolite formation, when podiform chromitites and their harzburgite–dunite hosts formed in the mantle wedge.

Once obducted and emplaced on continental margins, these SSZ ophiolites evolve into long-lived, low-temperature hydrogen systems. This evolution, from active forearc serpentinization to final obduction, is summarized schematically in our conceptual model (Figure 2). The inherited architecture illustrated there, with highly serpentinized, high-permeability corridors flanked by thick panels of relatively weakly serpentinized, chromitite-bearing harzburgite–dunite, allows large volumes of Fe^{2+} -bearing peridotite to remain reactive for hundreds of millions of years. Where meteoric water can circulate along reactivated fault zones and fracture networks, hydrogen generation and leakage can be sustained over at least 300 Myr, provided that fracture permeability is maintained or periodically reactivated and that fresh dunite, harzburgite and chromitite bodies remain available. This behavior is consistent with thermodynamic constraints on low-temperature

continental serpentinization fluids (Leong & Shock, 2020) and with observations of sustained H₂ production in partially hydrated peridotites in the Samail ophiolite, Oman (Templeton et al., 2024). Together, these studies indicate that efficient H₂ generation does not require high-temperature hydrothermal systems, but can persist under relatively cold, near-surface conditions when appropriate redox gradients and catalytic phases are present.

Within this framework, podiform chromitite bodies and their surrounding damage zones emerge as prime internal targets within such ophiolites. Our analyses emphasize that, at present, chromitite-bearing SSZ ophiolites are the best-documented natural laboratories for long-term, low-temperature hydrogen generation and, together with their adjacent sedimentary basins, should constitute priority targets for systematic exploration. The conceptual evolution shown in Figure 2 links the forearc serpentinization stage, through subduction choking, expulsion tectonics and final obduction, to the present configuration where preserved, chromitite-rich mantle panels are reconnected to meteoric fluids and operate as long-lived H₂ factories.

From a practical exploration perspective, the two massifs studied here provide useful first-order numbers. In both Kempirsay and Bulqizë, all documented H₂ seeps occur within the damage zones surrounding mapped podiform chromitite bodies, and individual vents display instantaneous flow rates between ~20 and 550 m³ day⁻¹. These values are strictly site-specific and based on a limited number of measurements, so they should not be taken as universal averages. They nevertheless illustrate the characteristic length scale of chromitite-centered damage zones and the potential magnitude of local hydrogen fluxes that can be sustained over geological timescales in such ophiolitic systems. More broadly, SSZ ophiolites appear to be the most fertile H₂ systems currently identified. They may locally host economically interesting accumulations, but probably of limited size because the petrophysical properties of these rocks restrict porosity to fractures. However, surrounding and overlying sedimentary basins may represent more favorable exploration plays, as they can trap H₂ sourced from the ophiolite and are connected to the H₂ factory through active structural drains.

Figure 2. Conceptual 3-D model for the tectonic and hydrological evolution of chromitite-bearing SSZ ophiolites and their long-lived hydrogen systems. (a) Continental subduction beneath a supra-subduction-zone oceanic lithosphere. An inherited transform-related or extensional fault (red) cuts the mantle wedge and localizes hydration and serpentinization along a narrow damage corridor (green). A thick panel of weakly serpentinized harzburgite–dunite (light blue) remains comparatively intact and hosts podiform high-Cr chromitite lenses (dark grey). (b–c) Subduction choking, exhumation and expulsion. Continued underthrusting of buoyant continental crust jams the subduction zone, drives uplift and lateral transport of the ophiolite toward the foreland. Strain and fluid flow remain focused along the serpentinized corridor and inherited structures, while the chromitite-bearing mantle panel is transported as a coherent block to shallow crustal levels with limited internal disruption. (d) Final obduction and present-day configuration. The ophiolite slab is emplaced on the continental margin, with broad, weakly serpentinized mantle panels flanking a narrow, highly serpentinized corridor. Reactivation of this high-permeability corridor by meteoric water circulation reconnects chromitite bodies to fresh fluids and sustains low-temperature H_2 generation in preserved Fe^{2+} -rich mantle domains. Colors: pale yellow = continental crust; light blue = weakly serpentinized ophiolitic mantle; green = highly serpentinized damage zones; dark grey = podiform chromitite bodies (adapted from Agard et al., 2023).

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